

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of some Azinate Complexes with Titanium(IV) and Zirconium(IV)

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Complexes of Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} with furfuraldazine, 2-thiophenaldazine and 2-pyridinaldazine have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance and ir and uv spectral data. Molar conductance values suggest that the complexes are 1 : 4 electrolytes in 10⁻³ M DMF solutions. The ir spectra reflect the involvement of only three coordination sites of the azine ligands in bonding to metal ions. The formula [ML₃]X₄ (where L=azine ligand ; X=Cl⁻ or NO₃⁻ ion ; M=metal ion) has been proposed for the complexes.

THE azines derived from 2-heterocyclic aldehyde are versatile ligands and can coordinate to metal ions in different manners. The two nitrogen atoms of the azine group are adjacent to each other and four coordination sites are available in these azines. Stratton and Busch¹ studied the metal complexes of azine derived from 2-pyridinealdehyde with Fe^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}. In recent years, an increasing number of metal complexes of azine derived from salicylaldehyde have been studied². This azine ligand appeared to act also as tridentate ligand by utilising both the hydroxyl groups and one of the azomethine groups as bonding sites.

In the present work, new metal-azine complexes are reported. The azines used are derived from furfural (FA), 2-thiophenealdehyde (TA) and 2-pyridinealdehyde (PA).

Experimental

Preparation methods :

Furfural, 2-thiophenealdehyde and 2-pyridinealdehyde were purified³. The azines were prepared by standard method⁴. For the preparation of the complexes, methanolic solutions of metal salts (TiCl₄ and Zr(NO₃)₄·5H₂O) were treated separately with methanolic solutions of azine ligands in 1 : 2 ratio, followed by refluxing the mixture for 1 h, then evaporated to about dryness, the solid product was washed with methanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Conductivity measurements were carried out with a MC-1 instrument using 10⁻³ M DMF solution at room temperature.

Elemental analysis of C, H and N were obtained using a Carlo-Erba-Strumentazione 1106 analyser.

The chloride content was estimated by potentiometric titration with AgNO₃ after decomposition of the complexes by sodium fusion. The metal content was determined by using a Pye-Unicam SP 9 atomic absorption spectrometer. The infrared spectra (KBr) were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (10⁻⁵ M MeOH) on a Shimadzu 210 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data for the metal complexes are given in Table 1.

The ir spectra of the azine ligands show a sharp band with medium intensity at 1 640–1 625 cm⁻¹ due to azomethine C=N stretching vibration¹. This band splits into two upon complexation, one appearing at frequency essentially the same as in the free ligand, whereas the other at lower frequency. This indicates that only one nitrogen atom of the azine group is coordinated to the central metal ion. It is difficult for the two adjacent nitrogen atoms of the azine group to coordinate with the same metal ion because of steric strain. The ir band for the ligands at 1 490, 1 300 and 1 580 cm⁻¹ due to C=O=C⁵, C=S=C⁶, and C=N=C¹ stretching vibrations respectively, have undergone positive shift upon complexation, suggesting the presence of a M-R bond (where M=metal ion and R=O or S or N). Such increase in frequency upon complexation may be related to an increase in the dipolar contribution of C=R=C⁷.

Therefore, the azine ligands with four coordination sites can act only as tridentate ligands by utilising both the C=R=C (from two heterocyclic rings)

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES*

Compd. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
				C	H	N	M	Cl	
1	[Ti(FA) ₂]Cl ₄	Dark brown	170d	41.55 (42.41)	2.04 (2.83)	9.35 (9.90)	7.79 (8.46)	24.60 (25.09)	300
2	[Ti(TA) ₂]Cl ₄	Brown	190d	38.74 (38.10)	2.93 (2.54)	8.35 (8.89)	7.46 (7.60)	22.33 (22.54)	308
3	[Ti(PA) ₂]Cl ₄	Dark brown	230d	47.03 (47.22)	3.69 (3.28)	17.83 (18.36)	7.21 (7.85)	22.75 (23.28)	300
4	[Zr(FA) ₂](NO ₃) ₄	Black	168	33.12 (33.56)	2.82 (2.24)	14.89 (15.66)	11.88 (12.75)	—	310
5	[Zr(TA) ₂](NO ₃) ₄	Yellow	180	30.19 (30.80)	2.63 (2.05)	13.32 (14.37)	10.98 (11.70)	—	320
6	[Zr(PA) ₂](NO ₃) ₄	Brown	158	38.36 (37.93)	2.01 (2.63)	21.76 (22.13)	11.56 (12.01)	—	300

*FA=2-furanaldazine, TA=2-thiophenaldazine and PA=2-pyridinaldazine; all complexes are very soluble in DMF and DMSO, and moderately soluble in MeOH.

groups and one of the azomethine groups as bonding sites.

The positive shift in N-N vibration on complexation can be added as a further support to the coordination of nitrogen atom to metal ion⁸. The ir spectra of zirconium complexes show a strong band at 1370 cm⁻¹, this may be assigned to ionic NO₃⁻ group⁹.

The ligands show two absorption bands A and B in the region 240–350 nm (Table 2). The band-A, (around 250 nm) may be assigned to local excitation of the heterocyclic ring¹⁰, whereas the band-B may be associated with $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ taking origin from heterocyclic ring and extending over the azine group¹⁰.

(362–395 nm) may be related to additional $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition involving metal and ligands orbitals.

The values of molar conductance (300–320 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate that all the complexes behave as 1 : 4 electrolytes¹¹.

The elemental analysis, molar conductance values, the spectral observations and the possibility of coordination number six in Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV}, indicate that the complexes have the formula [ML₂]X₄, where L=tridentate azine ligand, and X=Cl⁻ or NO₃⁻ ion.

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TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd.*	λ_{max} , nm ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$)		
	Band-A	Band-B	Other bands
FA	240 (4.4)	335 (20.3)	—
TA	245 (4.9)	330 (18.3)	—
PA	258 (8.3)	301 (16.9)	—
1	263 (6.5)	341 (22.7)	390 (3.1)
2	260 (6.2)	340 (23.5)	395 (3.3)
3	267 (9.3)	815 (16.1)	375 (3.3)
4	258 (6.1)	345 (22.8)	387 (3.9)
5	255 (5.4)	338 (22.3)	377 (3.3)
6	261 (8.9)	309 (13.3)	362 (3.1)

*Compound nos. correspond to the complexes in Table 1.

When the electronic spectra of the azine ligands are compared to those of the corresponding metal complexes, a great similarity is observed below 350 nm. The band above 350 nm in the complexes